

***Hippasa holmerae* Thorell (Araneae: Lycosidae): a new predator of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers**

Alberto T. Barrion, research assistant, and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Hippasa holmerae Thorell, a lycosid spider, inhabits dryland areas such as earthen embankments of irrigation canals or reservoirs near paddy fields in the Philippines. It seeks shelter in soil crevices and actively moves over the water surface in search of prey on rice plants. When caged on rice plants infested with brown and whitebacked planthoppers or green leafhoppers, the spider readily preys on those species. It also was observed to prey on two species of legume insect pests: *Amrasca biguttula*

(Shiraki) and *Ophiomyia phaseoli* (Tyron).

The adult spider can readily be distinguished from other paddy field lycosids by the slightly procurved anterior and strongly recurved posterior eyes; the presence of three promarginal and retromarginal teeth on the chelicerae; brown legs and cephalothorax; slant posterior region of the carapace; longitudinal black band on the midsternum; brown cardiac area on the dorsum of the dark brown abdomen; and large posterior spinnerets, which are twice the length of those in the anterior position (see figure).

Hippasa holmerae is a new item for the Philippines and Asian checklist of spiders inhabiting rice fields. ■

Hippasa holmerae Thorell, female dorsal view (a) and epigynum (b).

***Parasa bicolor* (Walk), a new pest of rice in Manipur**

S. Amu Singh, pest surveillance officer, Agriculture Department, Mantripukhri, Imphal, Manipur, India 795002

During the 1980 kharif, *Parasa bicolor* (Lepidoptera: Limacodidae) was widespread in hundreds of acres of rice in the east district of Ukhrul state, where shifting/terrace rice cultivation is practiced. An average of 35% damage to the standing rice crops was caused by the insect in Kamjong areas of the district. But in some pockets of Phungyar subdivision, the loss of the standing crops was above 90%.

Larvae, active in the morning, consume leaves from the tips toward the base. Several popular local varieties of rice — Sangsun, Tarangphou, Meiringnu, Bumpani, Angangphou, Changbi, and Singuingou — are susceptible to the insect.

So far, the insect has not been found on either high-yielding varieties or local varieties grown in the valley rice belt of the central district of the State. However, when the insects were released in the laboratory, the entire foliage of a 9-11 tiller-hill of IR24 was eaten by 3-4 caterpillars within 48 hours. In the

laboratory, the insects fed on seedlings as well as young transplanted plants. In the fields, the plants in the maximum tillering to early flowering stages were more susceptible to the pest.

The insect has been identified as

Parasa bicolor (Walk) by Dr. Y. S. Rao of the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India. This report constitutes the first one on the occurrence of this pest on rice in Manipur. ■

Effects of method of nitrogen application on the incidence of rice leaffolder

R. Saroja, Syed Nazeer Peeran, and N. Raju, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tirur, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, India

Studies on the effect of nitrogen levels on the occurrence of leaffolder on rice

have revealed that pest infestation increased with increasing nitrogen level. An experiment conducted at PES, Tirur, in the 1979-80 samba (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec) showed that a significant increase in percentage of leaffolder damage to leaves was achieved only by a very high level of nitrogen — 200 kg N/ha. The N was applied basally (1/2 the amount) and topdressed in 2 doses, 25 and 45 days after transplanting (DT).

Effect of nitrogen levels and method of application on leaffolder damage to rice at 60 DT^a, 1979-80 samba, Tamil Nadu, India.

Application method	Leaves damaged by leaffolder (%)		
	75 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha	Mean ^b
All N applied basally	11.7	30.4	21.1 c
1/2 N basal + 1/2 N topdressed	7.3	20.4	13.9 b
All N applied by applicator at 15 DT	9.0	12.1	10.6 b
All N applied by paper balls at 15 DT	8.9	11.5	10.2 b
1/2 N by applicator at 15 DT + 1/2 N topdressed at 35 DT	11.1	10.8	10.9 b
1/2 N by paper balls at 15 DT + 1/2 N topdressed at 35 DT	13.2	14.7	14.0 b
No nitrogen	5.3	4.8	5.1 a

^a DT = days after transplanting. ^b Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

The effect on leaffolder damage of different methods of applying nitrogen was investigated further in a split-plot design with two nitrogen levels (main treatment) and seven methods of application (subtreatments). In some treatments N as urea was applied to the root zone

with an applicator or by hand in paper balls. Fenitrothion (0.05%) was sprayed at 40 DT, and fenthion (0.05%) at 55 DT. Leaffolder infestation was assessed by recording the percentage of damaged leaves at 60 DT when the pest occurrence was highest.

Applying all the N basally tended to increase the leaffolder damage level above that with use of other methods (see table). But at a moderate N level, the application method appeared to have little effect on leaffolder damage. ■

Pest management and control WEEDS

Propagation of perennial paddy weeds in unplanted paddy fields

Jiro Harada, Hokuriku National Agricultural Experiment Station, Joetsu, Niigata 943-01, Japan

Recent agricultural policy on surplus rice in Japan increased the unplanted paddy fields all over the country. Perennial paddy weeds proliferated in such fields and their propagules were spread by plowing and puddling. This seems to be one reason for the recent rapid increase of perennial paddy weeds.

To determine the propagation ability of a single plant in unplanted paddy fields, an experiment used five serious perennial paddy weeds: *Sagittaria pygmaea* Miq. (Sp), *Cyperus serotinus* Rottb. (Cs), *Eleocharis kuroguwai* Ohwi (Ek), *Scirpus planiculmis* Fr. Schm. (Spl), and *Potamogeton distinctus* A. Benn. (Pd). The field was plowed and puddled after a uniform application of 50 kg N/ha, 100 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 100 kg K₂O/ha. One plant of each weed was transplanted in the center of a 9-m² plot separately on 10 June 1981. Hand weeding was carried out to avoid the effect of other weeds. The number of plants, the occupied land area, and the plant den-

Distribution map of perennial paddy weeds propagated from a single plant. Niigata, Japan, 1980.

Propagation from a single plant of perennial paddy weeds in an unplanted paddy field. Niigata, Japan, 1980.

Weed species	Plants ^a (no.)	Occupied land area ^a (m ²)	Density ^a (plants/m ²)	Propagules ^b	
				No.	Fresh wt (g)
<i>Sagittaria pygmaea</i>	313	0.939	333.3	822	41.1
<i>Cyperus serotinus</i>	321	1.551	210.8	794	190.0
<i>Eleocharis kuroguwai</i>	51	0.793	71.9	51	68.2
<i>Scirpus planiculmis</i>	214	3.494	61.2	1,244	1295.9
<i>Potamogeton distinctus</i>	457	2.615	174.8	118	24.7

^aExamined on 5 August 1980. ^bExamined on 12 November 1980.

sity were examined on 5 August and the propagules formed were examined on 12 November.

The results are shown in the figure and the table. Considerable propagules

were formed even in the least propagated weed. The results suggest that a few weeds remaining in the unplanted part of a paddy field is a big source of propagules for the following year. ■

Efficiency of fluchloralin, butachlor, nitrofen, and hand weeding for rice weed control

S. K. Mukhopadhyay and A. Mondal, College of Agriculture (P.S.S.), Visva-Bharati University, India

A field experiment at the Agricultural College Farm (Palli Siksha Sadana),

Sriniketan, Visva-Bharati, West Bengal during 1979 kharif studied the comparative efficiency of some granular herbicides and hand weeding for controlling weeds in the semihumid lateritic tract of the state. There were 12 weed species: 3 were grasses, 3 were sedges, and 6 were broadleaved of which *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, and *Ludwigia perennis*

were predominant in the experimental field. The granular herbicides fluchloralin at 2.0 kg a.i./ha 7 days after transplanting (DT), nitrofen 1.5 kg and 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT, and butachlor at 2.0 kg a.i./ha 6 DT reduced the weed population but showed no injurious effect on the crop (see table). Nitrofen and butachlor gave very promising results in